

Electron transfer kinetics of the reduction of bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) in an alkaline medium

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Abstract : This review highlights the reactivity of bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) towards different inorganic and organic substrates reported during the period 1989 until 2007. The inorganic substrates are reducing nitrobenzene, phosphorus, organophosphorus compounds and reducing organic substrates like alkanols, aryl alcohols, diols, aldehydes (aliphatic, aromatic, heterocyclic) and α,β -unsaturated compounds. All these reactions were studied in alkaline medium and the reactions exhibit diverse mechanistic behavior. Kinetics and mechanistic aspects of the reactions have been analyzed. An attempt has been made to correlate the results of different redox processes involving bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III).

Keywords : Review, oxidation-reduction reactions, bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III), reducing substrates.

Introduction

Copper is known to exist mainly in copper(I), copper(II) and copper(III) oxidation states¹. The copper(0) and copper(IV) states are extremely limited. Copper(IV) has only been characterized by two or three compounds² with the most electronegative ligands F⁻ and O²⁻. Copper(III) which is isoelectronic with nickel(II) occurs in several crystalline compounds but it is unstable in solution. Copper is found in both plants and animals. A number of copper proteins including enzymes have been isolated³. Known copper proteins are predominantly reversible oxygen carriers but little detailed chemical and structural information is yet available⁴. It has attracted interest in redox and kinetic investigations.

Copper(III) is prepared by the oxidation of two lower oxidation states. However [Cu(OH₂)₆]³⁺ is not known⁵ and the hypothetical [Cu(OH)₄]⁻ anion is very unstable. Copper(III) encountered least because of its high reduction potential⁶ ($E_0 > 1.8$ volt). Hypervalent metal ions, which play important role in biological systems, are generally stabilized through complexation with various ligands. The use of oxy anions such as (TeO₆)⁶⁻ and (IO₆)⁵⁻ resulted in the preparation of some relatively stable complexes of copper(III) even from aqueous solution. Different copper(III) complexes have also been isolated⁷. Of the different copper(III) complexes diperiodatocuprate(III) and bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) are known to exist in which copper(III) is in low spin state, the copper having a square planar arrangement of oxygen atoms^{7(b)}.

Considerable amount of work has been done on the oxidation of different reducing substrates by diperiodatocuprate(III)⁸ and bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) complexes in alkaline medium. In this review we mainly highlight the oxidations of different reducing inorganic as well as organic substrates by bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) under comparable experimental conditions and an attempt has been made to analyze and correlate the published results of the redox reactions.

Previous work

Tri-positive copper was first reported in 1844 and history up to 1925 of compounds of copper(III) has been reviewed by Vrtis⁹ and Malaprada¹⁰ who succeeded in isolating sparingly soluble sodium diperiodatocuprate(III), Na[Cu(IO₆)₂]. The work of Vrtis⁹, Malaprada¹⁰ and Malatesta¹¹ have established beyond doubt that copper(II) may be oxidized by potassium persulphate to copper(III) which is stabilized by coordination with a suitable anion like periodate or tellurate.

The kinetics for the homogeneous reduction of cuprate(III) were studied by Rozovskis *et al.*¹² in KOH solution (0.5–6) mol dm⁻³. The reduction of cuprate(III) to cuprate(II) takes place by a first order reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constant increases with increase in [OH⁻] and reaching a constant value at > 4 mol dm⁻³ [OH⁻]. The reduction mechanism is quite complex and not completely known. Mechanism for reduction of [Cu(OH)₂(H₃TeO₆)₂]⁵⁻ has also been studied¹³ by the same authors in KOH solution containing TeO₄²⁻. The reaction

shows a complex dependence of the rates of OH⁻ concentration, but inverse dependence on TeO₄²⁻. The kinetic data are explained by the formation of the intermediate, [Cu(OH)₂(H₂TeO₆)Cu(OH)₂]²⁻.

Copper(III) is a suitable oxidant for the titrimetric determination of some carbonyl compounds¹⁴. The number of equivalents of the oxidant consumed depends on the number of oxygen atoms required for the oxidation of these carbonyl compounds to CO₂ and H₂O stage. The first use of copper(III) as an oxidant in titrimetry was made by Beck¹⁵⁻¹⁹. He employed copper(III) for the titrimetric determination of some reducing sugars^{15,16}, glycerol¹⁷, amino acids¹⁸ and proteins¹⁹. He also deduced the constitution of proteins from characteristic curves obtained by differential titration of proteins with copper(III) solution²⁰.

The reaction²¹ of bis-2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline-cuprate(I) and bis-2,9-dimethyl-4,7-diphenyl-1,10-phenanthroline-disulfonate cuprate(I) with copper(III)-oligopeptide complex are quite rapid with rate constants varying from (2.0 × 10⁴ to 2.5 × 10⁸) mol⁻¹ dm³ s⁻¹, indicating that outer-sphere electron transfer occurs. The cross exchange rate constants *k* for the reactions Cu^{III}(peptide) + Cu^IL₂ → Cu^{II}(peptide) + Cu^{II}L₂, where L is dmp or dmp²⁻, were determined for a series of copper(III) peptides, where the E⁰ values vary from -0.11 to +0.32 volt.

Results

Oxidation of inorganic compounds by copper(III) :

Kinetics of the oxidation of different compounds of nitrogen and phosphorous by bis(dihydrogentellurato)-cuprate(III) have been studied spectrophotometrically as well as titrimetrically in an alkaline medium. The reaction of nitrite ion by copper(III) was carried²² out in the temperature range 298–313 K in (0.5–10.5) × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ alkaline medium keeping ionic strength. The reaction is first order with respect to [Cu^{III}] but the order with respect to [NO₂⁻] is complex. The rate of the reaction decreases with increase in [OH⁻]. Copper(III) oxidizes NO₂⁻ to NO₃⁻. The reaction takes place through the intermediate formation of the free radical according to the steps (1-5).

The following rate expression has been deduced :

$$-d[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}]/dt = \frac{k_1 K_1 [\text{NO}_2^-][\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_1 [\text{NO}_2^-]} \quad (I)$$

The kinetic investigations of the oxidation of N₃⁻ by bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) was studied^{23(a)} by varying hydroxide ion in the range (1–20) × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³. Ionic strength of the reaction medium was kept constant 0.95 mol dm⁻³. The reaction is first order with respect to [Cu^{III}] but the order with respect to [N₃⁻] is complex. The product N₂ is formed by one electron transfer oxidation process whereby copper(III) is reduced to copper(II). Evidence for the formation of N₃⁻ has been shown. The steps of the reaction are the following :

The reaction mechanism shows that OH⁻ ion retards the rate of oxidation, which is supported by the following rate expression.

$$-d[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}]/dt = \frac{k_2 K_2 [\text{N}_3^-][\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_2 [\text{N}_3^-]} \quad (II)$$

The values of K₂ (equilibrium constant for the formation of the complex between the reactants) and k₂ (disproportionation constant of the complex) were found to be 0.735 and 4.0 × 10⁻⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 303 K, respectively obtained from the substrate effect.

The oxidation of hypophosphite²⁴ and phosphite²⁵ by ditelluratocuprate(III) have been studied in alkaline medium over a wide range of temperature. Copper(III) is reduced

to copper(II). Two alternative Schemes-one involving two one-electron transfer steps with the intermediate formation of a free radical and another involving a two electron transfer step with the formation of Cu^I followed by a fast reaction between Cu^I and Cu^{III} have been proposed.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Each reaction is first order with respect to [Cu^{III}] as well as [HPO₃²⁻] or [H₂PO₂⁻]. The rate of reaction is independent of the alkali concentration in the range (0.35–3.6) × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at constant ionic strength. However, the pseudo-first order rate constant increases with increase in salt concentration, which may be due to the involvement of similar charged ions.

Oxidation of organic compounds by copper(III) :

The reactivities of some alkanols by bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) have been studied²⁶ in alkaline medium. The oxidation of the alkanols occur as shown in eq. (12), where, R₁ = R₂ = H for methanol; R₁ = H, R₂ = -CH₃ for ethanol; R₁ = R₂ = -CH₃ for isopropanol.

The reactions are first-order in [Cu^{III}] and [R₁R₂CHOH]. However, the rate was found to be independent of [OH⁻] in the concentration range (0.5–3.5) × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³. The reaction takes place via one electron transfer process according to the following steps.

The appearance of white precipitate in presence of 40% (w/v) acrylamide indicated the presence of free-radical intermediate which corroborated the above mechanism. The oxidations of benzyl alcohol and some substituted

benzyl alcohols (XC₆H₄CH₂OH, where X = -NO₂, -Cl and -OMe) towards this oxidant have also been studied^{26,27(a)} in alkaline medium and observed similar type of one-electron transfer step with intermediate formation of free radicals. OH⁻ ions have no effect on the reaction studied in the range (0.7–4.2) × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ of [OH⁻]. The experiments involving the oxidations of aryl alcohols were carried out in *tert*-butyl alcohol (15% v/v) since the substituted benzyl alcohols are insoluble in water.

Oxidative cleavage of some diols like ethylene glycol, butane-2,3-diol, pinacol and propane-1,2-diol towards bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) have been investigated²⁸ in alkaline medium. The reactions are first-order each in [Cu^{III}] and [diol], but the rate is independent of [OH⁻]. The oxidation of vicinal diols occur as shown in eq. (16), where, R₁ = R₂ = H for ethylene glycol; R₁ = R₂ = -CH₃ for pinacol; R₁ = H, R₂ = -CH₃ for butane-2,3-diol.

Diols are oxidized through the intermediate formation of free radicals followed by the rupture of C–C bond to give carbonyl compounds (eqs. 17–19).

α- and β-glycerophosphates are oxidized by bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) in alkaline medium²⁹. The reactions were studied in the temperature range 298–310 K keeping constant ionic strength. The reactions are first-order each in [Cu^{III}] and [glycerophosphate]. The pseudo-first order rate constant increases with increase in [OH⁻] in the oxidation of α-glycerophosphate but OH⁻ ion has no effect on the reaction rate in the oxidation of β-glycerophosphate. Since in the oxidation of α-glycerophosphate the rate is directly proportional to [OH⁻], it is believed that OH⁻ reacts with the terminal -CH₂OH group of α-compound to give alkoxide ion. On the other hand, since both the terminal -CH₂OH group of β-glycerophosphate are bonded to anionic sites of the phosphate group, the possibility of the formation of alkoxide has been totally ruled out during the reactions

of β -compound with Cu^{III} . The oxidation of α -glycerophosphate with ditelluratocuprate(III) take place according to Schemes 3 and 4.

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

The rate of disappearance of Cu^{III} may be expressed by eq. (III).

$$-d[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}]/dt = \frac{\{k_4 + k_3K_3[\text{OH}^-]\}[\text{RCH}_2\text{OH}][\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}]}{1 + K_3[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \text{(III)}$$

Since K_3 is small, $1 \gg K_3[\text{OH}^-]$, the equation changes to

$$-d[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}]/dt = \{k_4 + k_3K_3[\text{OH}^-]\}[\text{RCH}_2\text{OH}][\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}] \quad \text{(IV)}$$

The reactivity of a few aliphatic aldehydes, XCHO (where, $\text{X} = \text{H}$ -, Me -, MeCH_2 -, Me_2CH -), a number of aromatic aldehydes, $\text{YC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CHO}$ (where, $\text{Y} = \text{H}$ -, $-\text{NO}_2$ -, $-\text{Cl}$ and $-\text{OMe}$) and 2-furaldehyde towards ditelluratocuprate(III) were studied³⁰ in alkaline medium. The reactions of aromatic aldehydes were studied in *tert*-butyl alcohol (15% v/v). The reaction is first order with respect to [aldehyde]. The values of k_{obs} were found to be independent of initial $[\text{OH}^-]$. Irrespective of whether the substrate is aliphatic, heterocyclic or aromatic aldehyde, the reaction with Cu^{III} takes place via one electron transfer process according to the steps (20-23).

The reaction step (20) shows that oxidation occurs via C-H bond cleavage, which supported by the kinetic isotope effect.

The reduction of bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) by α, β -unsaturated compounds, $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHX}$ ($\text{X} = -\text{CN}$, $-\text{CONH}_2$ and $-\text{CO}_2^-$) have been studied³¹ in $(0.14-1.20) \text{ mol dm}^{-3} [\text{OH}^-]$ at constant ionic strength. The reactions were studied over the 298–318 K temperature range. The rate of the reaction is dependent on the first power of the concentration of substrate, oxidant, and alkali. The reactions follow the rate law :

$$-d[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}]/dt = k_3'[\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}][\text{CH}_2=\text{CHX}][\text{OH}^-] \quad \text{(V)}$$

The values of the third order rate constant (k_3') for the oxidation of acrylonitrile, acrylamide and acrylate are 2.42×10^{-2} , 1.67×10^{-2} and $1.10 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. The reaction takes place through the intermediate formation of free radical in a slow step followed by its decomposition to give diols.

The major reaction products, glyceronitrile, glyceramide and glycerate ion of the oxidations of the respective substrate by Cu^{III} , were identified using column chromatography and IR spectrometry.

Rajeswari and Vani have studied the oxidation of DL-methionine³² by ditelluratocuprate(III) in alkaline medium and observed one electron transfer mechanism with the intermediate formation of free radicals. DL-Methionine is oxidized to methioninesulphoxide under the experimental conditions. Hydroxyl ion inhibits the rate of oxidation. The reactions of few aliphatic amines by copper(III) in alkaline medium proceeds³³ through the initial formation of adduct between amine and copper(III) followed by its decomposition to give the reaction product. The rate increases with increase in ionic strength. The reactivity of amines towards copper(III) follows the order : secondary > primary > tertiary.

The reactions of some aliphatic ketones by copper(III) have been investigated³⁴ by Murthy *et al.* in alkaline medium. The reaction involves the enol form of the ketone in a slow step. The oxidation of 2-hydroxy butyric acid salt and 3-hydroxy butyric acid salt by copper(III) have recently been studied³⁵ over the temperature range 298–313 K. The reaction is first-order with respect to [oxidant] and a complex order with respect to [substrate]. Hydroxyl ion increases the rate of oxidation, but the rate of reaction

has an inverse dependence on $[\text{TeO}_4^-]$. The rate of the reaction was dependent on the position of hydroxyl group.

Discussion

The oxidations of different inorganic and organic substrates have been studied in alkaline medium. Hydroxyl ion plays important role in determining rate and mechanism of some reactions. The rate of the reaction is independent of $[\text{OH}^-]$ in the oxidations of H_2PO_2^- , HPO_3^{2-} , β -glycerophosphate, alkanols, aryl alcohols, vicinal diols, aliphatic, heterocyclic and aromatic aldehydes. The rate however decreases with the increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ in the oxidations of NO_2^- and N_3^- . On the other hand, the rate increases with the increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ in the oxidation of α -glycerophosphate. The reactions occur through the intermediate complex formation between the reactants in the oxidations of NO_2^- and N_3^- by copper(III) whereas kinetic evidence for intermediate complex formation is insignificant in the oxidations of other inorganic and organic substrates.

The oxidation of NO_2^- by copper(III)²² in alkali medium proceeds through the formation of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{TeO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_3\text{NO}_2]^{5-}$ between the reactants in which

OH^- is replaced by NO_2^- , which is bonded to Te. The rate decreases with increasing $[\text{OH}^-]$ which may be due to acid-base equilibrium. This electron transfer possibly occurs through the oxygen bridge of the copper(III) complex leading to the formation of free radical, NO_2^\cdot . The free radicals react with further with copper(III) to give NO_3^- in alkaline medium. The greenish-blue precipitate obtained from the reaction mixture was removed by filtration. The filtrate was tested by the addition of nitron, a voluminous precipitate was obtained indicating that nitrite had been oxidized to the nitrate stage. The green precipitate was dissolved in dil. HClO_4 and to it NH_3 solution was added. A blue colour appeared, indicating that coordination sphere of copper(III) has been altered.

The kinetic results of the oxidation of N_3^- by copper(III)^{23(a)} indicate that the reaction proceeds with the intermediate formation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{TeO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_3\text{N}_3]^{5-}$, leading to its decomposition to give products through the generation of free radical, N_3^\cdot . The intermediate formation of azide radical, N_3^\cdot has also been reported in the reduction of manganese(III) by azide ion in acid media^{23(b)}. The cyclic voltammogram of ditelluratocuprate(III) in aqueous solution showed an irreversible reduction at -0.506 V at 298 K. The current peak height of the cyclic voltammogram of

Cu^{III} reduction is comparable to the height of the peak of reference standard one-electron redox system of ferrocene-ferrocenium under identical conditions, thus ruling out the possibility of the reduction of Cu^{III} to Cu^I. The oxidation product containing dry argon gas was passed through a solution of [Ru(NH₃)₅H₂O]²⁺ which gave a solid complex [(NH₃)₅Ru(N₂)Ru(NH₃)₅]⁴⁺. The isolated solid complex exhibited a strong Raman band around 3100 cm⁻¹, indicating the existence of N≡N bond. The Raman band confirmed that N₂ was formed as the oxidation product of N₃⁻. Again on standing the reaction mixture for several hours, a green precipitate was found. The precipitate washed thoroughly, dried and analyzed (Found : Cu, 44.1. Calcd. for Na₂CuO₂ : Cu, 44.7%). The room temperature magnetic moment (*ca.* 25 °C) of the solid has been found to be 1.27 B.M.

Hypophosphite ion (H₂PO₂⁻) is oxidized^{24(a)} by Cu^{III} to the phosphite (HPO₃²⁻) state. Since the concentration of phosphite ion is very small, further oxidation of phosphite ion does not occur. Copper(III) in ditelluratocuprate(III) is surrounded by a square planar arrangement of oxygen atoms. It is suggested that the inactive form of hypophosphite ion (H₂PO₂⁻) enters into the coordination sphere of the complex forming an unstable intermediate. This decomposes to give reaction products in a one-electron transfer process (Scheme 5). When the concentration of HPO₃²⁻ > 3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Cu^{III} oxidizes²⁵ HPO₃²⁻ to HPO₄²⁻ according to the Scheme 6. HPO₄²⁻ subsequently by reacting with Cu^{II} gives insoluble potassium copper(II) phosphate (Found : Cu, 27%. Calcd. for KCuPO₄·2H₂O : Cu, 27.7%). Thermo-gravimetric analysis of the solid product indicated that loss of water of crystallization takes place in two steps. The room temperature magnetic moment of the solid complex was found to be 1.35 B.M. From the EPR spectrum of the solid complex 'g' value has been calculated to be 2.11243

('g' value for free electron = 2.00023). It may be mentioned that 'g' values (>2.1) for different copper(II) complexes have also been obtained^{24(b-d)}.

Carbonyl compounds were identified as the only organic product for the oxidation of alcohols by copper(III)^{26,27(a)}. Formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, acetone, benzaldehyde and benzophenone are formed in the oxidations of methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, benzyl alcohol and benzhydrol by copper(III), respectively. Since the rate is independent of [OH⁻], it is suggested that Cu^{III} reacts with simple alcohol molecule instead of alkoxide ion. The oxidations of alkanols and [O-D] alkanols were found to be same under identical experimental conditions. These results indicate that oxidations of the alcohols by Cu^{III} do not occur via O-H bond fission but rather C-H bond cleavage. Similar kinetic isotope effects have also been observed in the oxidations of some alkanols and aryl alcohols by gold(III)^{27(b)} in acidic medium where the oxidations have been shown to occur via C-H bond fission. Thus, the radical intermediate R₁R₂·COH, formed in the slow step (13), further reacts with another Cu^{III} to give R₁R₂CO and Cu^{II} as shown in fast step (14). The reactivity of alkanols towards copper(III) follows the order : ethanol > methanol > 2-propanol and that of substituted aryl alcohols NO₂ > H > Cl > OMe. The order is in agreement with those reported earlier for the gold(III) oxidations of the same alcohols^{27(b)}. The unsubstituted benzyl alcohol reacts at faster rate with Cu^{III} than the corresponding reactions of benzhydrol. The slow rate in benzhydrol possibly due to steric hindrance of the second phenyl group on the alcohol carbon renders the reaction less favourable³⁶. The value of ρ was calculated to be 0.76 from the least square plots of log k_{obs} vs σ.

The oxidation²⁸ of ethylene glycol, 2,3-butanediol and pinacol by Cu^{III} leads to the formation of formaldehyde, acetaldehyde and acetone, respectively. Initial attack of Cu^{III} on H-C-O-H (the hydroxy hydrogen) is preferred to that on H-C-O-H (the α-H) in the oxidation mechanism,

Scheme 7

Scheme 8

leading to the formation of free radicals and ditelluratocopper(II). The formation of intermediate free radicals is supported by the observed polymeric suspension in the presence of acrylonitrile. The free radicals react further with copper(III) to give carbonyl compounds and the green product, $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_6)_2]^{6-}$, indicating that reactions occur by an inner-sphere mechanistic path. In the stable conformation of ethylene glycol, two -OH groups are in the *gauche* form and hence the reaction takes place as shown in Scheme 7. In the stable conformation of butane-2,3-diol the two -OH groups are farthest apart (Scheme 8) and hence in the transition state 'B' there is electronic assistance of the methyl group but there is no hindrance by the -OH groups as they are in staggered conformation unlike the transition state 'A' in ethylene glycol, where the -OH groups are in skew conformation. Thus the rate of reaction of butane-2,3-diol is faster than ethylene glycol. Again the formation of the transition state 'C' by the attack of Cu^{III} on pinacol is less favoured than the butane-2,3-diol due to steric hindrance caused by two methyl groups on each carbon atom of the pinacol molecule (Scheme 9), but once the transition state 'C' is formed, the bond breaking will be highly favoured due to release of steric strain in the transition state.

In modern biology, it is becoming daily evident that phosphorus compounds play a major role in the life process³⁷. Many of the biologically important compounds are the organic orthophosphates. Of the different organic orthophosphates, glycerophosphates, which are known to exist in α - and β - forms, occupy important

positions in metabolic processes and are compounds of immense biological importance³⁸. Reactions of glycerophosphates with metal ions will naturally be an important aspect for investigation from mechanistic viewpoint. Kinetic results indicate²⁹ that the reaction occurs through C-H bond cleavage with the formation of free radicals which then decompose to give phosphoglyceraldehydes as shown in Schemes 3 and 4. No attempt has been made to compare the rate of α - and β -glycerophosphates since the substrates are oxidized by different mechanistic path. The oxidation products of α -glycerophosphate and β -glycerophosphate have been identified²⁹. It has been shown that C-O-P bond cleavage to give glycerol and phosphoric acid followed by the oxidation of glycerol to give glyceraldehyde does not occur³⁹. On standing the reaction mixture with excess copper(III) for several hours a light blue precipitate was formed which was filtered off, washed, dried and analyzed (Found : Cu, 14.9. Calcd. for $\alpha\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_7\text{P}_2\text{Cu}$: Cu, 14.6%. Found : Cu, 14.8. Calcd. for $\beta\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_7\text{P}_2\text{Cu}$: Cu, 14.6%). The room temperature magnetic moments of the solid compounds were calculated to be 1.55 and 1.39 B.M. for α - and β - respectively, which are much less than the theoretical value⁴⁰, 1.73 B.M. From the EPR spectrum of the solid complexes g -values have been calculated which are found to be 2.1045 and 2.1095 for α - and β - respectively.

The influence of substituents on the reaction rate of the oxidation of aldehydes under similar experimental conditions indicate that the aliphatic aldehydes react with copper(III) at much faster rates than heterocyclic and aromatic aldehydes³⁰. The pseudo-first order rate constant

Scheme 9

Scheme 10

in the reaction of aliphatic aldehydes, 2-furaldehyde and benzaldehyde with Cu^{III} follow the order: $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}- > \text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2- > \text{CH}_3- > \text{H}- > \text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{O}- > \text{C}_6\text{H}_5-$. The least squares plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs σ^* (the polar substituent constant) gave ρ^* (susceptibility of the reaction of polar effect) value of -2.5 ($r = 0.8957$). Again, of the different nuclear substituted benzaldehyde, NO_2 -compounds react at much faster rates than the corresponding Cl - and CH_3O -substituted derivatives and the oxidation rate follow the order: $-\text{NO}_2 > -\text{H} > -\text{Cl} > -\text{OCH}_3$. The rate of oxidation of benzaldehyde thus increases with the presence of an electron withdrawing group and decreases with an electron donating group. Similar observation has also been reported in the oxidation of aldehydes by MnO_4^- in alkaline medium⁴¹. The value of ρ has been calculated to be 0.85 from the least squares plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs σ (Hammett substituent constants) for *meta* and *para* substituted compounds. The oxidation of benzaldehyde and benzaldehyde- d_1 by Cu^{III} were carried out under similar

experimental conditions and the value of $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$ was found to be 4.50. The observed isotopic and substituent effects indicate that the reaction occurs through C-H bond cleavage in the slow step, leading to the intermediate

Fig. 1. EPR spectrum of the reaction mixture containing benzaldehyde and Cu^{II} at different time intervals

Scheme 11

formation of free radicals⁴². The formation of intermediate free radicals is supported by the observed polymeric suspension in the presence of acrylamide. Although the reactions have been shown to proceed through one electron transfer process, the involvement of single two-electron mechanism (Scheme 10) cannot be totally ruled out. The observed substituent and isotope effects may be explained by the mechanism as shown in Scheme 10. The possibility of proton transfer during the reaction may be accelerated in the presence of electronegative substituent that converts III to the products. The appearance of acrylamide polymerization could be due to the formation of free radicals in the secondary reaction (step V-VI) as shown in Scheme 10. The EPR spectrum of the reaction mixture containing benzaldehyde and Cu^{III} complex indicate that peak intensity increases with increase in time due to the formation of Cu^{II} species during the reaction (Fig. 1). This was further supported by the EPR spectrum of the blue cuproammonium complex.

Fig. 2. EPR spectra of the green solid products obtained in the oxidations of (a) CH₂=CHCN, (b) CH₂=CHCONH₂ and (c) CH₂=CHCOO⁻ by copper(III) at microwave frequency.

During the oxidation of α,β -unsaturated compounds, the electron transfer takes place between HOCH₂C⁻HX and copper(III)³¹ in a slow step with the formation of intermediate transition state. The intermediate immediately decomposes to HOCH₂C[·]HX and Cu^{II} (Scheme 11). The overall oxidation reaction follows the outer-sphere mechanism followed by steps (26) and (27). The free radicals react with Cu^{III} to give diols as the final product as shown in fast step (26) and (27). The presence of -CN group facilitates the formation of carbanion thereby increasing the reaction rate, whereas the rate decreases considerably when COO⁻ is present. The reaction rate which follows the order : -CN > -CONH₂ > -COO⁻ supports the above contention. A similar reaction order was also noticed in the oxidation of these α, β -unsaturated compounds by pentachlorohydro-xoplatinum(IV)^{43(a)} and bromate ion^{43(b)}. The substrate are oxidized to glyconitrile, glyceramide and glycerate ion, respectively. After the kinetic experiments the reaction mixture were filtered to remove solid green product. The green precipitates were dissolved in dilute perchloric acid and then made ammonical when a deep blue color appeared which indicated that Cu^{III} was reduced to Cu^{II}. The solid Cu^{II} compounds were analysed (Found : Cu, 7.7. Calcd. for K₆[Cu(H₂TeO₄)]·4H₂O : Cu, 7.7%). Thermo-

Fig. 3. Isokinetic correlation for the oxidation of some organic compounds by copper(III). Plot of ΔS^\ddagger versus ΔH^\ddagger . (a) Alcohols^{26,27(a)} and glycerophosphates²⁹; (b) diols²⁸; (c) aldehydes³⁰; (d) α,β -unsaturated compounds³¹.

Table 1. The values of second-order rate constants ($k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[S]$), equilibrium constant (K) for the fast step, dipropionate constant (k) for the slow step for the oxidation of some inorganic compounds by ditelluratocuprate(III)

Substrate	[OH ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ k_2 (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ k (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	K	Ref.
NO ₂ ⁻	0.105	—	1.60 ± 0.08	9.55 ± 0.37	22
N ₃ ^{-a}	0.20	—	4.0 ± 0.2	0.74 ± 0.04	23(a)
H ₂ PO ₂ ⁻	0.025	42.4 ± 1.69	—	—	24
HPO ₃ ²⁻	0.025	2.93 ± 0.15	—	—	25

The values of k_2 , k and K were obtained at 298 K unless stated otherwise. The errors correspond to two least-squares standard deviations ($\pm 2\sigma$).

^aAt 303 K.

gravimetric analysis of the solid product indicated the four molecules of water of crystallization. The EPR spectrum of the solid product (Fig. 2) indicates that Cu^{III} is reduced to Cu^{II}. The g values were found to be 2.032 ± 0.005 as compared to that of 2.0023 for unpaired electrons.

Kinetic results and different thermodynamics parameters of different reactions are recorded in the Tables 1–3. An attempt was made to correlate the activation parameters of the oxidations of inorganic and organic

substrates. The plot of ΔS^\ddagger vs ΔH^\ddagger is not linear in the oxidations of inorganic substrates. This is to be expected since these reactions occur by different mechanistic paths. On the other hand the plots of ΔS^\ddagger vs ΔH^\ddagger for the oxidations of different organic substrates are linear and different lines were obtained for different series of reactions (Fig. 3).

It has been observed that bis(dihydrogentellurato)-cuprate(III) is reduced to give copper(II) in these redox reactions to give free radicals. The existence of free radical

Table 2. The values of second-order rate constants ($k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[S]$) for the oxidation of organic compounds by ditelluratocuprate(III)

Substrate	10 ² k_2 (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Ref.	Substrate	10 ² k_2 (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Ref.
Methanol	0.356 ± 0.02	26	Formaldehyde	9.53 ± 0.3	30
Ethanol	0.40 ± 0.02	26	Acetaldehyde	31.2 ± 1.4	30
Isopropanol	0.111 ± 0.005	26	Propionaldehyde	236.6 ± 1.7	30
Benzylalcohol	17.8 ± 0.9	26	Isobutyraldehyde	536.6 ± 1.66	30
	8.53 ± 0.2 ^a	27			
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzylalcohol	10.23 ± 0.33	27	2-Furaldehyde	9.1 ± 0.3	30
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzylalcohol	12.8 ± 0.27	27	Benzaldehyde	3.46 ± 0.1 ^c	30
				2.25 ± 0.14	30
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylalcohol	16.6 ± 0.26	27	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	6.67 ± 0.31	30
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzylalcohol	5.85 ± 0.13	27	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	4.17 ± 0.17	30
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzylalcohol	7.13 ± 0.2	27	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	4.98 ± 0.27	30
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzylalcohol	8.2 ± 0.2	27	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	2.08 ± 0.082	30
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzylalcohol	4.6 ± 0.13	27	<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	1.92 ± 0.096	30
<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzylalcohol	6.6 ± 0.14	27	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	0.93 ± 0.042	30
<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzylalcohol	7.67 ± 0.23	27	<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	1.28 ± 0.05	30
Ethylene glycol	8.9 ± 0.4 ^b	28	<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	0.95 ± 0.05	30
Butane-2,3-diol	36.7 ± 1.8 ^b	28	<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzaldehyde	0.72 ± 0.03	30
Pinacol	32.2 ± 1.28 ^b	28	Acrylonitrile	0.312 ± 0.012 ^d	31
Propane-1,2-diol	22.4 ± 0.9 ^b	28	Acrylamide	0.189 ± 0.0009 ^d	31
			Acrylic acid	0.128 ± 0.005 ^d	31

The values of k_2 were obtained at 298 K unless stated otherwise. The oxidation involving aromatic aldehydes and substituted benzyl alcohols were studied in *t*-butyl alcohol (15% v/v) unless otherwise mentioned. ^aIn 15% *tert*-butyl alcohol. ^bAt 283 K. ^cIn aqueous medium. ^dAt [OH⁻] = 0.24 mol dm⁻³.

Table 3. The values of thermodynamic parameters associated with the equilibrium step and activation parameters for the slow step for the oxidation of inorganic compounds by ditelluratocuprate(III)

Substrate	ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Ref.
NO ₂ ⁻	25 ± 2	103 ± 7	72 ± 2	-74 ± 7	22
N ₃ ⁻	27 ± 2	19 ± 7	83 ± 1	-37 ± 4	23(a)
H ₂ PO ₂ ⁻	-	-	48 ± 2	-112 ± 7	24
HPO ₃ ²⁻	-	-	52 ± 2	-119 ± 7	25

intermediates in the decomposition of copper(III)tetramine complexes have been previously demonstrated^{44,45}. There is also evidence in the literature⁴⁶ to indicate that methyl ethyl ketone and cyclohexanone reduce Cu^{III} in an one electron transfer process to afford copper(II). Considerable amount of work has been done on the copper(II) oxidations of organic compounds which have been reviewed⁴⁷. Since then some other useful information on the redox reactions involving copper(II) in solution has been obtained^{48,49} from photo induced and luminiscent measurements. The redox properties of dinuclear copper(II) complexes have received extensive attention using cyclic voltammetry measurements^{50,51}. Photoacoustic spectroscopy has also been used to study the redox process on the surface of an electrode using copper metal in alkaline solution⁵². The E⁰ values of different Cu^{II}/Cu^I systems are generally described in terms of the ligands present in solid state and the standard electrode potentials as a function of ligand environment have been measured⁵³. The standard redox potential of Cu³⁺ + e → Cu²⁺ is > 1.8 V as compared to the values of Cu²⁺ + e → Cu⁺ which are 0.153, 0.688 and 0.25 V in H₂O, C₅H₅N and dioxane, respectively. Hence in contrast to copper(III), copper(II) is relatively mild oxidant. Thus the possibility that copper(II) further oxidizes the unreacted substrates has been ruled out rather copper(II) reacts with the different oxidation products to give different copper(II) compounds which have been isolated and characterized. The EPR spectrum of the reaction mixtures in solutions of different reactions have been recorded at different time intervals. The peak intensity increases with increase in time. This is possibly because of the formation of paramagnetic d⁹ copper(II) species with the progress of the reaction. Again in the oxidations of α,β-unsaturated compounds by platinum(IV)^{43(a)} the reactions occur by single two electron transfer process in alkaline medium unlike the oxidation of the same substrates by bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) which takes place by free radical mechanism. The enthalpies and entropies of activation for the two electron transfer process as have

been obtained with platinum(IV) are smaller as compared to those obtained in the studies where copper(III) behaves as an one electron transfer oxidant.

Experimental

Absorbances were measured on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were studied on a Perkin-Elmer 298 spectrometer. EPR spectra were recorded with a Varian EPR spectrometer. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded by a Bio-Analytical Systems (BAS) CV-27 instrument in a dry Ar atmosphere using a three-electrode configuration. Thermogravimetric analysis was performed in a Shimadzu Corporation (Japan) TG50 in a normal atmospheric environment.

Ditelluratocuprate(III) solution was prepared⁵⁴ by heating a mixture of copper(II)sulphate, potassium tellurite and potassium persulphate solution in KOH solution. The mixture was boiled with constant stirring until it was intense red and then heated for further few minutes to eliminate excess persulphate. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and filtered. A solution of NaNO₃ was added to the filtrate and left overnight. The light red crystals were filtered off and washed with water. IR spectrum of the solid compound was found to remain unaltered with the literature value⁵⁵. The absorption spectra of copper(III) solution in the concentration range (1.0–7.5) × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ were studied in the UV-vis region. The aqueous solution of copper(III) complex shows two bands at 274.5 and 407.5 nm. The values are in good agreement with the reported value⁵⁵, namely 274 ± 2 and 406 ± 3 nm. Beer's law has been found to be valid in the concentration range studied. The solution of ditelluratocuprate(III) thus obtained was estimated by iodometric method in presence of sodium arsenite. The reaction mixture was then acidified with dil. H₂SO₄ until the green suspension disappeared. A solution of NaHCO₃ was added to the reaction mixture and the excess arsenite was back titrated against standard I₂ solution using starch indicator.

Most of the kinetic investigations were studied

spectrophotometrically using Systronic (India) spectrophotometer filled with thermostated cell compartment. The rate of decrease of copper(III) was monitored at the absorbance maximum of copper(III) complex. The pseudo-first order rate constants were evaluated from the plots $\log A$ (A = absorbance) vs time. The rate of decrease of copper(III) in alkaline medium may also be followed titrimetrically for some reactions under pseudo-first order conditions. Solutions of Cu^{III} and the mixture containing substrate and OH^- were separately thermostated (± 0.1 °C) for nearly 1 h before the kinetic run. The reaction was started by adding the oxidant to the other reactants and was followed by transferring aliquots of the mixture at different time intervals into a known excess of sodium arsenite solution. The un-consumed arsenite was acidified with dilute sulfuric acid and titrated against standard iodine using starch indicator.

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Sen Gupta *et al.* : Electron transfer kinetics of the reduction of bis(dihydrogentellurato)cuprate(III) in an alkaline medium

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